

Image Steganography with Open SSL Base64 Encryption for Enhanced Password Security

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Abstract: To provide increased data security, image steganography algorithms can be used with encryption methods. This paper proposes using the Least Significant Bit algorithm in conjunction with the OpenSSL Base64 encryption approach to create a two-layer password security system. To hide data, the suggested approach exploits one of the three colours contained in each image pixel (RED, GREEN, or BLUE). This approach successfully conceals data in an image that contains the LSB of BLUE colour pixel value with no major changes in the picture colors. This approach for concealing information in photos improves on the Least Significant Bit (LSB) approach.

Keywords- Cipher text, Image Steganography, LSB Image Steganography, OpenSSL Base64 encryption, Stego image

I. INTRODUCTION

Steganography is the notion of storing data in a way that conceals its existence. Steganography is the use of cover media such as text, audio, video, and picture to disguise data from attackers who are unaware of the original message contained in the media or the technique used to embed or extract it.

For data encryption and decryption, ciphering techniques are commonly employed. However, data encryption may not always appear to be safe enough. As a result, a higher level of information concealment is required. Steganography is the methodology used to implement this concept.

A collection of pixels makes into a picture. To show the image, these pixels are arranged horizontally row by row. The LSB, which substitutes the least significant bits of pixels selected to disguise the data, is the most well-known Steganography approach that operates in the spatial domain. This approach comes in a variety of implementations, each of which improves the algorithm in different ways.

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II. LITERATURE REVIEW

There are a multitude of approaches for implementing steganography on various electronic mediums. Md. Rashedul Islam, Ayasha Siddiqa, Md. Palash Uddin, Ashis Kumar Mandal, and Md. Delowar Hossain suggested an idea employing AES encryption and LSB steganography. Before the secret information is put in the LSB image, it is encrypted with a secret key.

By examining the MSB of pixel values, this approach looks for brighter and darker pixel portions in an image and saves information in either of them. As a result, this approach does not make efficient use of an image's storage space.

Mr. Vijay Kumar Sharma, Vishal Shrivastava, proposed an enhanced LSB substitution approach for concealing one image within another picture. An image's MSB pixel values are retrieved and then integrated into another image's LSB pixel values (cover image). This hides the fact that a picture exists. However, after being recovered from the stego picture with minimal distortion, the quality of the embedded picture would be compromised.

Mrs. Kavitha, Kavita Kadam, Ashwini Koshti, and Priya Dughav suggested the notion of steganography with an extra authorisation mechanism at the time of data embedding and retrieval using the LSB replacement approach. As a

result, unauthorised workers will not be able to harm the data. The suggested approach has a major drawback in that it is only suited for bit map pictures (.bmp). As a carrier file, it only takes bit map images, and the compression relies on the document size and carrier image size.

Simple LSB picture steganography without any extra security is suggested by Amritpal Singh and Harpal Singh. This approach merely arranges the data inside the picture in a predetermined sequence. As a result, this strategy is incompatible with sensitive or confidential data. In comparison to previous ways, this strategy is less complicated and needs less time and space.

III. PROBLEM DEFINITION

The program's main goal is to use the least significant bit steganography technique to encrypt and conceal data or information over a picture, and then save the picture on the server. The image with the hidden message is known as the cover picture, and the picture with the secret message is known as the stego picture.

A. The problem's solution

This technique was created to conceal information in any picture file. This technique creates a stego picture from the cover file, which will be used to hide the contents following OpenSSL Base64 encryption. When obtaining data from a picture, the suggested technique should provide higher security and dependability. As a result, data encryption, decryption, and steganography all play a role.

B. The Technique Employed (LSB Algorithm)

For encryption, the "Encryption phase" employs two sorts of objects. One is a secret key that should be kept safe, while the other is a cover file like picture[1]. The data is encrypted using the OpenSSL Base64 encryption technique, and the encrypted data is stored in the picture using the Least Significant Bit algorithm (LSB), which swaps the cover picture's least significant bits with the bits of the encrypted secret data.

The stego picture in which the data is concealed is delivered as an input file in the "Decryption phase." The encoded bits in the picture are retrieved using the Least Significant Bit technique (LSB), and the output is a cypher text. To prevent unwanted data access, the decryption step employs the same secret key that was used for encryption. The secret key is then used to decrypt the encrypted text and retrieve the original content.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The suggested approach is divided into two parts:

- Using the OpenSSL Base64 encryption method, convert the secret message (plain text) to cypher text.
- Using the LSB Steganography method to hide the cypher in the picture.

For example, suppose the data "XYZ" has the following attribute and is stored in the first 8 pixels of a 200 by 400 pixel picture with 24 bits per pixel.

LETTER	ASCII VALUES	BINARY VALUES
X	88	01011000
Y	89	01011001
Z	90	01011010

Each pixel has three bytes: one for the Red colour, one for the Green colour, and one for the Blue colour. The actual colour of that pixel is determined by the combination of these three colours.

If we wish, we may modify the LSB of all Red, Green, and Blue components. Human eyes see red as the most dominant colour, whereas blue is the least dominant.

As a result, the colour blue was chosen so that no one would guess the presence of the message within the image.

To begin, turn the secret message into a cypher value. Let's say we wish to use this approach to hide the character "X" in the cypher text. Then, for each pixel in the picture, retrieve the RGB value. Then convert the character 'X' to its ASCII value (88), and finally to binary format (01011000). We need 8 pixels of the picture because we're concealing 8 bit info. We'll replace the final bit of each pixel's RGB value with the appropriate binary value of text in order for the first 8 pixel values. As a result, the new RGB value is:

- 11001100 10010001 00101010
- 10010001 11110000 11111111
- 00100101 11100010 01010100
- 11100010 00001010 01000011
- 11001100 11111101 00101011
- 00011000 11110000 11111110
- 00100101 11100010 01010100
- 11111101 00001010 01000010

The highlighted bit represents the message we are hiding in the image. We set the new RGB value to the pixel. This change is not detected by human eye and the image looks exactly the same.

V.IMPLEMENTATION

Step 1: Users log in with their passwords, which are encrypted using the OpenSSL Base64 encryption algorithm and a randomly generated secret key.

The registration form titled 'Register Here' contains three input fields: 'Email Id' with a placeholder 'Enter Email Id', 'Password' with a placeholder 'Enter Password' and a 'Show' button, and 'Confirm Password' with a placeholder 'Confirm Password' and a 'Show' button.

Figure 1: Registration Form

Step 2: The server creates the relevant stego picture and stores the encrypted password in it.

Figure 2: Stego Image

Step 3: Encrypt the random secret key with md5 and save it in the database.

User Id	Secret Key
Akhil0505	0288e85cc6fce438abb6fafcf1bc8009

Table 1: Secret Key stored in Database

VI. RESULTS

The present LSB method has a greater space and temporal complexity. The suggested method's average computing time was determined to be around 2.2 seconds. The resolution of the source image selected for steganography determines the size of the stego picture, which is independent of the size of the hidden message.

As a result, by employing a low-resolution image as the cover picture, the space complexity may be decreased. The space and time complexities of this technique are minor when compared to the increased data security.

Cover Image	Username	Password	Secret Key (MD5 Encoded)
Img.jpeg	akhil0505	akh0505	0288e85cf5hhc e438abb6f afcf1 df9

Table 2: Values before OpenSSL Base64 Encryption

Cipher Text	Stego Image
eBwbWXzwmyi1T0UhfO x5nD8lJymj RpMgrwi7WMsxbw0AhcGb z+ZsEJeNv +IGPFsUEVnVriQi/0kkmiF 9f5TVFblW a3JbjnED6OcnWNPPhKiWG NFloEizsE 7uzllr1Tb	Akhil0505.jpeg

Table 3: Values after OpenSSL Base64 Encryption

VII. CONCLUSION

The use of steganography as a data protection strategy is expected to grow in relevance. To create a safe way of information storage, we printed out the scope of the LSB image steganography system paired with the OpenSSL Base64 encryption approach. Without the secret key, even if the user obtains the stego picture, he is unable to extract the original data. As a result, additional security is added to the standard Steganography methodology. A true colour picture was used to separate the cover item into multiple colour zones. The secret data was embedded in the image after it was divided into various colours such as red, green, and blue during the processing.

This study presents a double-layer security

steganography technique. The suggested approach was used to build a stego picture. It is discovered that the quality of the stego picture does not have any significant distortion while using the suggested approach (as seen by the naked eyes). As a result, this algorithm is particularly effective at hiding sensitive info via graphics. Various users can utilise the Stego picture to hide data inside the image without disclosing the secret data to third parties. It protects critical data, such as passwords, from prying eyes. Steganography is a valuable tool for enhancing the security of traditional encryption.

VII. REFERENCE

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